

A COMPARISON OF CURRENT DESIGN CONCEPTS OF FUSELAGE PANELS UNDER TYPICAL LOAD CONDITIONS

X. Cai^{1*}, F. Dervault², S. V. Hoa¹, R. Sedaghati¹

¹ Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Concordia University, Montreal, Canada, ² Advanced Structure, Bombardier Aerospace, Montreal, Canada

* Corresponding author (x_ca@live.concordia.ca)

Keywords: *design concepts of fuselage panel, advanced composite materials, business jet*

Abstract

This paper presents a side-by-side comparison of common design concepts employed in the practice of sizing metallic/composite fuselage panels by the aerospace industry with respect to structural weight. The study shows that composite fuselage panels could achieve a lighter design compared with metallic fuselage panels by 10-20% approximately. The design of fuselage panels is driven by the design constraints described in the paper. Moreover, it provides guidance to structural engineers for selecting proper design concepts for a fuselage panel with the minimal structural weight. For example, it is shown that orthogrid and generalgrid are preferred for the design of metallic crown and side fuselage panels. T inverted and L stiffened panels are mostly suitable for the design of metallic keel panel. T inverted and L stiffened panels are recommended for the sizing of composite crown and side panels. T inverted and Z stiffened panels are the best for the sizing of composite keel panel.

1 Introduction

Fuselage design has been evolving progressively since the first creation of Wright Flyer I by the Wright Brothers in 1903. Design concepts, for example truss structure, geodetic structure, monocoque shell, semi-monocoque shell, and sandwich construction, have been developed to optimize aerodynamic characteristics, increase load-carrying capacity, and minimize structural weight [1, 2]. Many of these concepts have been implemented in the engineering design of modern military and commercial aircrafts that already entered into the service. However, it is hard to conclude that one design is superior to the others without a fair comparison. The objective of this study is to carefully review 18 selected panel design concepts used in the design of fuselage panels and rank them by evaluating their structural efficiencies and

eventually provide design recommendations to structural engineers on the selection of the proper panel design concepts. HyperSizer 6.4.50 developed by Collier Research was utilized to size and optimize the structural components of the fuselage panels subjected to typical external loads at three functional areas, namely crown, side, and keel panels of a fore fuselage section as shown in Fig. 1. Although this study is mainly targeted on the design of the composite fuselage panels, it still requires the design of metallic fuselage panels which serve as a baseline for the purpose of comparison and validation. Three comparisons on the selected design concepts for the crown, side, and keel panels were conducted in the study. The paper starts from the description of fuselage panels, follows by the selection of design concepts, selection of materials, external loads, design requirements, design approach, and ends with results and conclusions.

Fig. 1 Illustration of three functional areas at fore fuselage of Bombardier business jet (Photo courtesy of Bombardier Aerospace)

2 Description of Fuselage Panels

Three functional areas located at the fore fuselage section were chosen for this investigation. They are classified by the dominant loads applied. For instance, the crown panel is dominated by the tension load with a fraction of shear load due to fuselage bending. The side panel is subjected to a combination of tensile/compressive load and shear load induced by the fuselage bending as well. The keel area is prevailed with compression load with a

fraction of shear load as a result of dynamic landing. During drift landing, the shear load increases as compared to the normal landing condition. Moreover, ground loading such as taxi, autonomous turning and braking may be considered for specific local areas in the design phase. A typical stiffened fuselage for a business jet is defined as 16 in frame pitch and 6 in stringer spacing with a radius of curvature of 40 in. However, in the current study, the frame pitch was set to 32 in intentionally because the sandwich and grid stiffened panel require a much larger frame pitch than the uniaxial stiffened panel. The panel width was set at 32 in to accommodate at least four stringers with a spacing of 8 in, and the radius of curvature of the fuselage panel was set at 46.06 in. Additionally, the stringer spacing is treated as a variable varying from 4 in to 7 in. Fig. 2 shows the dimensions of the fuselage panel.

Fig. 2 Dimensions of stiffened fuselage panel

3 Selection of Design Concepts

Five design concept families, namely unstiffened plate, sandwich panel, corrugated stiffened panel, uniaxial stiffened panel, and grid stiffened panel were evaluated. Bonded stiffener concept was selected for the design of the uniaxial stiffened panel to simplify the design process by bypassing the fastener analysis and design. In other words, it was assumed that stiffeners would be bonded with top/bottom faces by structural adhesives to maintain the structural integrity. However, statistical-based adjustment factors were applied to the metallic and composite designs to account for the weight added to the fuselage panels due to primer, sealant, lightning protection materials, and fasteners. Table 1 shows a breakdown of the adjustment factors recommended experienced engineers from Bombardier Aerospace. It is suggested to add 23% and 52% more weight to the metallic designs and composite designs respectively. A total of 18 candidate designs selected from five families were analyzed in accordance with identified load cases for each functional area described above. All the designs are tabulated in Table 2 and illustrated in Fig. 3.

Table 1 Breakdown of statistical-based adjustment factors for metallic and composite designs

Material Desity	AI 2024	AS4/3502	Unit
	0.101	0.057	lbs/in ³
Tolerancing	1	5	%
Primer	1	2	%
Copper Mesh	-	6	%
Surface Film	-	10	%
Sealant	1	2	%
Fasteners at Aircraft Level	8	12	%
Fasteners for System Installation	12	15	%
Total Weight	0.124	0.087	lbs/in ³
	123	152	%

Table 2 List of design concepts

Families	ID	Members
Unstiffened Plate	a	Unstiffened Panel
Sandwich Panel	b	Foam Sandwich
	c	Honeycomb Sandwich
Corrugated Stiffened Panel	d	Trusscore Sandwich
	e	Hat Stiffened Panel
	f	Two-Sheet Stiffened Panel
Uniaxial Stiffened Panel	g	Integrally Blade Stiffened
	h	Integrally T Inverted Stiffened Panel
	i	Integrally L Stiffened Panel
	j	Integrally Blade Stiffened Sandwich
	k	I Stiffened Panel
	l	T Stiffened Panel
	m	Z Stiffened Panel
	n	J Stiffened Panel
	o	C Stiffened Panel
Grid Stiffened Panel	p	Orthogrid
	q	Isogrid
	r	Generalgrid

Fig. 3 Illustration of design concepts listed in Table 2 (Photo courtesy of Collier Research)

4 Selection of Materials

An Al-Cu heat treatable alloy (Al 2024-T3) and a carbon fiber reinforced thermoset (AS4/3502) were used for the skin and stiffener of the sandwich and stiffened panels. SynCore 9823.1 film and HexWeb HRH-10-1/8-4.0 honeycomb were selected as the foam and honeycomb material respectively. The basic materials properties of these material systems are summarized in Table 3 to Table 6. Mechanical properties at room temperature were used throughout the calculations. It may underestimate the true extent of the structural efficiency of the composite panels since elevated temperature/wet properties are slightly lower than the room temperature ones.

Table 3 Mechanical properties of Al 2024-T3 (Thickness range 0.128 in, Basis A) [3]

Density	0.101 lbs/in ³
Thickness Range	0.128 in
Tensile Modulus	10.5 Msi
Compressive modulus	10.7 Msi
In-Plane Shear Modulus	4 Msi
Poisson's Ratio	0.313
Ultimate Tensile Strength	64 ksi
Tensile Yield Strength	47 ksi
Compressive Yield Strength	39 ksi
Ultimate Tensile Strength (LT)	63 ksi
Tensile Yield Strength (LT)	42 ksi
Compressive Yield Strength (LT)	45 ksi
In-Plane Shear Strength	39 ksi
Tensile Strain Allowable	4476.2 μin/in
Compressive Strain Allowable	3644.9 μin/in
Tensile Strain Allowable (LT)	4000 μin/in
Compressive Strain Allowable (LT)	4205.6 μin/in
Ultimate Shear Strain Allowable	9750 μin/in

Note: LT stands for long-transverse direction.

Table 4 Mechanical Properties of AS4/3502 slit tape [4]

Density	0.057 lbs/in ³
Tape Thickness	0.0055 in
Fiber Volume Fraction Ratio	60 %
0° Tensile Modulus	19.3 Msi
90° Tensile Modulus	1.35 Msi
0° Compressive modulus	18 Msi
90° Compressive modulus	1.41 Msi
In-Plane Shear Modulus	0.543 Msi
Out-of-Plane Shear Modulus	0.543 Msi
Poisson's Ratio	0.34
0° Tensile Strength	205 ksi
90° Tensile Strength	28.35 ksi
0° Compressive Strength	171 ksi
90° Compressive Strength	29.61 ksi
In-Plane Shear Strength	13.4 ksi
0° Tensile Strain Allowable	13250 μin/in
90° Tensile Strain Allowable	21000 μin/in
0° Compressive Strain Allowable	10725 μin/in
90° Compressive Strain Allowable	21000 μin/in

Table 5 Mechanical properties of Syncore 9823.1 [5]

Density	0.0243 lbs/in ³
Tensile Modulus	0.38 Msi
Compressive modulus	0.2 Msi
Shear Modulus	0.145 Msi
Ultimate Tensile Strength	4 ksi
Ultimate Compressive Strength	9 ksi
Ultimate Shear Strength	8.9 ksi

Table 6 Mechanical properties of HexWeb HRH-10-1/8-4.0 honeycomb [6]

Density	0.0023 lbs/in ³
Stablized Tensile Modulus	0.028 Msi
Stablized Compressive Modulus	0.028 Msi
L Direction Plate Shear Modulus	0.0086 Msi
W Direction Plate Shear Modulus	0.0047 Msi
Stablized Tensile Strength	0.47 ksi
Stablized Compressive Strength	0.47 ksi
L Direction Plate Shear Strength	0.225 ksi
W Direction Plate Shear Strength	0.115 ksi

5 External Loads

Four load cases were considered for sizing each functional area, which were representative of the ultimate loads exerted on the crown, side, and keel areas of a pressurized fore fuselage section during a typical flight mission. 77 discrete load cases for each functional area were extracted from the GFEM (generalized finite element model) of a Bombardier business jet. These discrete load cases simulate the actual external loads exerted on the fuselage panels from taxi to landing. Fig. 4 illustrates the balanced free body diagram of a typical fuselage panel with an indication of applied loads and internal pressure.

Fig. 4 Balanced free body diagram of fuselage panel

Fig. 5 shows the load distributions of the crown, side, and keel panels in terms of in-plane axial and shear loads. The load intensities used in the plot were approximated based on the average elemental forces over the area of interest. It was assumed that the loads in the hoop direction were neglected owing to the application of the internal pressure. The internal pressure was set at 18.67 psi for all designs. In addition, the effects of ambient temperature variations were ignored in the design.

Fig. 5 Load distributions of crown, side and keel fuselage panels

Fig. 6 shows three virtual design spaces of the external loads bounded with four extremum points for all three functional areas. The use of the virtual spaces considerably reduces the amount of work required for sizing fuselage panels by minimizing the number of load cases considered in the design. In this case, the number of load cases for each fuselage panel is reduced from 77 to 4. As a result, 12 load cases are required for the study which are tabulated are Table 7.

Fig. 6 Virtual design spaces of external loads for crown, side and keel fuselage panels

Table 7 Load cases for crown, side and keel panels

Load Case	N_x/N_{xy} (lbf/in)	Functional Area		
		Crown	Side	Keel
1		970/40	350/110	510/125
2		-230/40	-270/110	-665/125
3		-230/-30	-270/-275	-665/-140
4		970/-30	350/-275	510/-140

6 Design Requirements

A sound fuselage panel design must meet all the technical requirements and federal regulations to ensure safety and suitability for service. Mostly important ones are categorized and listed as follows:

- Structural features
 - Cutouts and holes
 - Structural joints
- External relations
 - Thermal loads
 - Mechanical loads
- Design requirements
 - Environment requirements
 - Onset buckling limitation
 - Damage tolerance requirements
- Other requirements
 - Material costs
 - Manufacturing costs
 - Producibility
 - Maintainability, inspectability, and repairability

They are equally important in the design of a fuselage panel. It is a false statement that the external loads are the primary driving factor for designing the fuselage panel. To keep the study concise and achievable within a limited timeframe, four of these technical requirements were selected and defined as design constraints in this study. First, the structural joint requirements placed a limitation on the fastened/bonded joint configuration between the skin and stringer. Second, the environment requirements imposed a constraint on the skin thickness of the fuselage panels to prevent potential damages from temperature and lightning strikes. Third, the damage tolerance requirements defined the minimum thickness for the crown, side and keel panels, which protect the fuselage panels from damages caused by hail strikes, ground debris and catway threats. Fourth, the manufacturing considerations defined the minimum thickness of the skin, stiffener, foam material, and honeycomb

material. In summary, the selected design constraints imposed on the design variables are tabulated in Table 8.

Table 8 Summary of design constraints for the design of fuselage panels

Design Variable	Minimum Requirement
1. Skin Thickness	≥ 0.04 in
2. Attached Flange Thickness	≥ 0.04 in
3. Free Flange Thickness	≥ 0.04 in
4. Attached Flange Width	≥ 0.500 in
5. Free Flange Width	≥ 0.100 in
6. Foam Thickness	≥ 0.010 in
7. Honeycomb Thickness	≥ 0.125 in

In addition, according to provided failure analyses in Hypersizer, the following analyses were performed for the metallic/composite fuselage panels for ensuring the structural integrity.

- Metallic material strength
- Ply-based composite material strength
- Laminate-based composite strength
- Panel buckling
- Stiffened panel flexural-Torsional buckling
- Stiffened panel local buckling
- Stiffened panel crippling
- Stiffened panel cross-section geometry checks
- Sandwich panel facesheet wrinkling
- Sandwich panel shear crimping
- Sandwich panel intracell dimpling
- Sandwich panel flat wise Tension
- Sandwich panel core shear strength
- Sandwich panel core crushing
- Bonded joints

7 Design Approach

The design of the crown, side and keel panels were carried out in Hypersizer, a structural sizing tool based on analytical formulas. The tool has limited optimization capabilities. It is capable of analyzing, from a structural standpoint, all design concepts presented previously in Table 2 while calculating minimal weight for each of them. In fact, it searches a candidate design with the lowest weight while meeting minimum margin of safety (default set at 0) among all combinations of design variables. Over 100 failure analyses can be activated via a sizing form in Hypersizer, which includes the ones required for this study. Unfortunately, the software does not update the searching direction and step size

of design variables at each iteration like other optimization algorithms. It poses a challenge on how to define variable range and the number of variable permutation with a limitation on the number of candidate designs. The risk of not finding the optimum point can be mitigated by starting with a large design space including infeasible solutions and testing multiple initial points evenly spread across the design space. As a result, the design space progressively reduces to a reasonable size. The variable range and the number of variable permutation can be further refined by the statistical optimization tool in Hypersizer. In summary, Hypersizer leaves the design space exploration/exploitation balance to software users. It evaluates all candidate designs defined by the users in terms of the panel weight. The sizing process starts by sorting all candidates in terms of unit weight, and then structural analysis is performed from the lowest weight candidate towards the highest one until all margins of safety reach the default or user defined values.

Additionally, controlling the number of candidate designs is equally important. The computation costs increase exponentially with an increase of the number of variable permutation. In particular, it is recommended to control the number of candidate designs as low as possible when sizing a composite fuselage panel. For a composite design, skin and stringer materials are considered as two independent variables as a function of the percentage of each fiber orientation in a laminate. This requires a tremendous amount of testing to find the best effective laminate and target thickness for each of them. Moreover, the percentage of each fiber orientation may be altered when creating a discrete laminate from the effective laminate due to the implementation of fundamental laminate design guidelines as follows.

- Laminates are required to be symmetric and balanced.
- Laminates are required to have at least 10% of their plies in each of the 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, and 90° directions.
- The maximum percentage of plies in any direction will be 60%.

There are inevitable limitations on the effective laminate approach in the composite design. For example, the failure analyses for an effective laminate may not be accurate because plies in the same directions are lumped in the laminate without the considerations of the design guidelines. In

addition, the ply continuity between adjacent fuselage panels is not considered which may lead to a failed design due to the poor producibility.

8 Results and Conclusions

The study comprises five parts, and the results for each part are presented in this section sequentially.

8.1 Effects of stringer spacing on unit panel weight without thickness and width constraints

The first part of the study focused on finding the relation between stringer spacing and unit panel weight for the uniaxial stiffened panel family. The stringer spacing was defined in between 2 - 7 in with an increment of 1 in. A metallic crown panel was selected as the object to study. The design constraints given in Table 8 were excluded from this part of the study. The local buckling analyses for the panel skin were performed based on the ultimate loads. The study results are tabulated in Table 9. The unit weights of the designed panels are plotted at varying stringer spacing in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Unit weights of uniaxial stiffened metallic crown panels at varying stringer spacing without selected design constraints

As can be seen in the figure, the stiffened panel weight increases gradually when adjacent stringers move apart from each other. Except for the blade stiffened sandwich, the others exhibit a similar increasing trend in the unit panel weight with an

increase of the stringer spacing. That implies that the structural efficiency of the uniaxial stiffened panel design concepts is comparable and the local buckling of unsupported skin is the driving factor for the design of the metallic crown panels. The skin buckling capacity increases with a reduction of the stringer spacing. However, the weight savings on the skin are offsetted by the weight added to the stringers.

8.2 Effects of stringer spacing on unit panel weight with thickness and width constraints

The second part of the study was an extension of the previous one, which intended to quantify the influences of the design constraints on the unit panel weight for the uniaxial stiffened panels. Two adjustments were made in the program. First, the minimum thickness and width constraints (refer to Table 8) were imposed on the designs. Second, the local buckling analyses for the panel skin were conducted based on the limit loads. Table 10 summarizes the study results, and Fig. 8 shows a plot of the unit panel weight as a function of the stringer spacing.

Fig. 8 Unit weights of uniaxial stiffened metallic crown panels at varying stringer spacing with selected design constraints

As it can be observed, the unit panel weight decrease until reaching an optimum point first, and then bounce back quickly. Comparing with the first part of the study, the mechanical performance of the

selected design concepts can be easily differentiated at the stringer spacing of 6 in. Three integrally stiffened panels are lighter than the others.

To have a better understanding on the influence of the design constraints on the panel design, at least one example design concept needs to be analyzed. Z stiffened panel was selected for the study. Fig. 9 shows the result for the unit panel weight against the stringer spacing for Z stiffened panel based on the first and second part of the study. As it can be realized, the panel design is driven by the minimum thickness and width constraints for the skin and stringer when the stringer spacing is less than 5 in. The discrepancy on the unit panel weight at the optimum stringer spacing is attributed to the choice of the limit loads or ultimate loads for the local buckling analyses. As expected, the design using the limit loads for the skin local buckling analyses is lower than the one using the ultimate loads. It is a common practice to perform the local buckling analysis on metallic stiffened panels at the limit loads for weight saving.

Fig. 9 Unit weight of Z stiffened metallic crown panel at varying stringer spacing with design constraints

8.3 Design of metallic and composite crown panel

The third part of the study included the design of the metallic and composite crown panels. The limit loads and ultimate loads were used in the local buckling analyses for the metallic and composite designs respectively. The study results are summarized in Table 11. Two statistical-based

adjustment factors of 1.23 and 1.52 were applied to the metallic and composite designs respectively to account for the weight added to the fuselage panels. Fig. 10 shows a parallel comparison of the metallic and composite crown panels designed with the selected design concepts on the normalized unit panel weight. Among the metallic design concepts, orthogrid is the most efficient one for the crown panel following by generalgrid, T inverted stiffened panel, L stiffened panel, and T stiffened panel. However, among the composite design concepts, T inverted stiffened panel is the lightest one following by L stiffened and blade stiffened panels. The composite designs are lighter than the metallic designs except for generalgrid. The weight savings due to the use of composite materials vary from 2% to 19%.

8.4 Design of metallic and composite side panel

Similarly, the fourth part of the study included the design of the metallic and composite side panels. The study results are organized into Table 12. Two statistical-based adjustment factors of 1.23 and 1.52 were also applied to metallic and composite designs respectively. Fig. 11 presents a parallel comparison of the metallic and composite side panels designed with the selected design concepts on the normalized unit panel weight. As it can be observed, among the metallic designs, orthogrid is the most efficient design concept for the side panel following by generalgrid and L stiffened panel, which is remarkably similar to the previous case of study. However, among the composite designs, L stiffened panel is the lightest design following by T inverted stiffened and I stiffened panels. The composite designs are lighter than the metallic designs except for those from the grid stiffened family. The weight

savings due to the use of composite materials vary from 10% to 31%.

8.5 Design of metallic and composite keel panel

Like last two parts of the study, this part of the study included the design of the metallic and composite keel panels. The study results are summarized in Table 13. Similarly, two statistical-based adjustment factors of 1.23 and 1.52 were applied to metallic and composite designs respectively. Fig. 12 provides a parallel comparison of the metallic and composite keel panels designed with the selected design concepts on the normalized unit panel weight. As it can be seen, among the metallic designs, T inverted stiffened and L stiffened panel are the most efficient designs for the keel panel followed by C stiffened panel. However, among the composite designs, T inverted stiffened panel is the lightest design followed by Z stiffened and L stiffened panels. The composite designs are lighter than the metallic designs except for isogrid. The weight savings due to the use of composite materials vary from 4% to 29%.

In summary, composite fuselage panels designed based on the room temperature properties are approximately 10-20% lighter than metallic fuselage panels. Orthogrid and generalgrid are preferred for the design of the metallic crown and side fuselage panels. T inverted and L stiffened panels are preferred for the sizing of the metallic keel panel. T inverted and L stiffened panels are mostly suitable for the sizing of the composite crown and side panels. T inverted and Z stiffened panels are recommended for the sizing of the composite keel panel.

Table 9 Unit panel weights for uniaxial stiffened fuselage panels without design constraints (Unit : lbs/ft²)

Families	Members	Stringer Spacing (in)					
		2	3	4	5	6	7
Uniaxial Stiffened Panel	Blade Stiffened Panel	0.653	0.727	0.784	0.821	0.832	0.884
	T Inverted Stiffened Panel	0.577	0.689	0.781	0.821	0.834	0.884
	L Stiffened Panel	0.568	0.697	0.781	0.821	0.833	0.884
	Blade Stiffened Sandwich	0.796	1.039	1.223	1.349	1.477	1.61
	I Stiffened Panel	0.563	0.666	0.755	0.793	0.806	0.812
	T Stiffened Panel	0.698	0.732	0.785	0.808	0.812	0.827
	Z Stiffened Panel	0.565	0.665	0.752	0.787	0.799	0.813
	J Stiffened Panel	0.569	0.664	0.738	0.778	0.797	0.808
	C Stiffened Panel	0.562	0.664	0.743	0.782	0.801	0.812

Table 10 Unit panel weights for uniaxial stiffened fuselage panels with design constraints (Unit : lbs/ft²)

Families	Members	Stringer Spacing (in)					
		2	3	4	5	6	7
Uniaxial Stiffened Panel	Blade Stiffened Panel	0.828	0.772	0.747	0.73	0.792	0.885
	T Inverted Stiffened Panel	0.91	0.8	0.747	0.727	0.79	0.886
	L Stiffened Panel	0.909	0.8	0.746	0.729	0.789	0.884
	Blade Stiffened Sandwich	1.311	1.31	1.401	1.552	1.707	1.866
	I Stiffened Panel	1.161	0.966	0.873	0.823	0.806	0.839
	T Stiffened Panel	1.155	0.964	0.876	0.834	0.817	0.85
	Z Stiffened Panel	1.005	0.863	0.805	0.768	0.759	0.824
	J Stiffened Panel	1.158	0.967	0.877	0.826	0.795	0.831
	C Stiffened Panel	1.004	0.864	0.801	0.77	0.817	0.836

Table 11 Unit panel weights of metallic and composite crown panels designed with selected design concepts

Families	Members	Metallic Design			Composite Design			Weight Saving	
		Corrected Unit Weight	Normalized Unit Weight	Ranking	Corrected Unit Weight	Normalized Unit Weight	Ranking		
		lbs/ft ²	lbs/ft ²		lbs/ft ²	lbs/ft ²		%	↑↓
		Unstiffened Panel	Unstiffened Panel	1.069	1.000	12	0.961	0.899	12
Sandwich Panel	Form Sandwich	1.624	1.519	16	1.587	1.485	16	-2%	↓
	Honeycomb Sandwich	1.849	1.730	17	1.689	1.580	17	-9%	↓
Corrugated Stiffened Panel	Trusscore Sandwich	2.151	2.013	18	1.794	1.678	18	-17%	↓
	Hat Stiffened Panel	1.124	1.052	13	0.971	0.909	13	-14%	↓
	Two-Sheet Stiffened Panel	1.454	1.360	14	1.190	1.113	14	-18%	↓
Uniaxial Stiffened Panel	Blade Stiffened Panel	0.900	0.842	6	0.748	0.700	3	-17%	↓
	T Inverted Stiffened Panel	0.894	0.837	3	0.736	0.688	1	-18%	↓
	L Stiffened Panel	0.894	0.837	3	0.737	0.690	2	-18%	↓
	Blade Stiffened Sandwich	1.610	1.506	15	1.392	1.303	15	-14%	↓
	I Stiffened Panel	0.978	0.915	10	0.790	0.739	5	-19%	↓
	T Stiffened Panel	0.894	0.837	3	0.872	0.816	10	-2%	↓
	Z Stiffened Panel	0.929	0.869	8	0.796	0.745	6	-14%	↓
	J Stiffened Panel	0.984	0.921	11	0.833	0.779	9	-15%	↓
	C Stiffened Panel	0.920	0.861	7	0.822	0.769	8	-11%	↓
Grid Stiffened Panel	Orthogrid	0.839	0.785	1	0.762	0.712	4	-9%	↓
	Isogrid	0.969	0.907	9	0.798	0.747	7	-18%	↓
	Generalgrid	0.876	0.819	2	0.891	0.833	11	2%	↑

Fig. 10 Comparison of metallic and composite crown panels designed with the selected design concepts in terms of the normalized unit weight

Table 12 Unit panel weights of metallic and composite side panels designed with selected design concepts

Families	Members	Metallic Design			Composite Design			Weight Saving %
		Corrected Unit Weight	Normalized Unit Weight	Ranking	Corrected Unit Weight	Normalized Unit Weight	Ranking	
		lbs/ft ²			lbs/ft ²			
Unstiffened Panel	Unstiffened Panel	1.840	1.000	16	1.578	0.857	16	-14% ↓
Sandwich Panel	Form Sandwich	1.704	0.926	15	1.526	0.829	15	-10% ↓
	Honeycomb Sandwich	2.305	1.253	18	1.696	0.922	17	-26% ↓
Corrugated Stiffened Panel	Trusscore Sandwich	2.154	1.170	17	1.750	0.951	18	-19% ↓
	Hat Stiffened Panel	1.125	0.612	8	1.003	0.545	9	-11% ↓
	Two-Sheet Stiffened Panel	1.458	0.792	13	1.205	0.655	14	-17% ↓
Uniaxial Stiffened Panel	Blade Stiffened Panel	1.096	0.596	7	0.947	0.515	4	-14% ↓
	T Inverted Stiffened Panel	1.041	0.566	4	0.904	0.492	2	-13% ↓
	L Stiffened Panel	1.038	0.564	3	0.901	0.490	1	-13% ↓
	Blade Stiffened Sandwich	1.610	0.875	14	1.111	0.604	12	-31% ↓
	I Stiffened Panel	1.130	0.614	10	0.906	0.492	3	-20% ↓
	T Stiffened Panel	1.178	0.640	12	0.985	0.535	8	-16% ↓
	Z Stiffened Panel	1.085	0.590	5	0.961	0.522	5	-11% ↓
	J Stiffened Panel	1.133	0.616	11	0.965	0.525	6	-15% ↓
Grid Stiffened Panel	C Stiffened Panel	1.085	0.590	5	0.965	0.525	6	-11% ↓
	Orthogrid	0.975	0.530	1	1.064	0.578	10	9% ↑
	Isogrid	1.127	0.612	9	1.164	0.633	13	3% ↑
	Generalgrid	0.999	0.543	2	1.096	0.596	11	10% ↑

Fig. 11 Comparison of metallic and composite side panels designed with the selected design concepts in terms of the normalized unit weight

Table 13 Unit panel weights of metallic and composite keel panels designed with selected design concepts

Families	Members	Metallic Design			Composite Design			Weight Saving %
		Corrected Unit Weight	Normalized Unit Weight	Ranking	Corrected Unit Weight	Normalized Unit Weight	Ranking	
		lbs/ft ²	lbs/ft ²		lbs/ft ²	lbs/ft ²		
Unstiffened Panel	Unstiffened Panel	1.828	1.000	16	1.547	0.846	17	-15% ↓
Sandwich Panel	Form Sandwich	1.734	0.949	15	1.451	0.794	16	-16% ↓
	Honeycomb Sandwich	1.836	1.005	17	1.386	0.758	15	-25% ↓
Corrugated Stiffened Panel	Trusscore Sandwich	2.182	1.194	18	1.865	1.021	18	-15% ↓
	Hat Stiffened Panel	1.248	0.683	8	1.006	0.550	6	-19% ↓
	Two-Sheet Stiffened Panel	1.522	0.832	13	1.247	0.682	12	-18% ↓
Uniaxial Stiffened Panel	Blade Stiffened Panel	1.325	0.725	11	1.134	0.620	8	-14% ↓
	T Inverted Stiffened Panel	1.121	0.613	1	0.942	0.515	1	-16% ↓
	L Stiffened Panel	1.121	0.613	1	0.976	0.534	3	-13% ↓
	Blade Stiffened Sandwich	1.610	0.881	14	1.143	0.625	9	-29% ↓
	I Stiffened Panel	1.226	0.671	6	0.998	0.546	5	-19% ↓
	T Stiffened Panel	1.349	0.738	12	1.188	0.650	11	-12% ↓
	Z Stiffened Panel	1.162	0.636	4	0.958	0.524	2	-18% ↓
	J Stiffened Panel	1.216	0.666	5	0.995	0.545	4	-18% ↓
C Stiffened Panel	1.161	0.635	3	1.039	0.568	7	-11% ↓	
Grid Stiffened Panel	Orthogrid	1.305	0.714	10	1.250	0.684	13	-4% ↓
	Isogrid	1.295	0.709	9	1.331	0.728	14	3% ↑
	Generalgrid	1.239	0.678	7	1.165	0.637	10	-6% ↓

Fig. 12 Comparison of metallic and composite keel panels designed with the selected design concepts in terms of the normalized unit weight

9 Future Work

This study shows that the stringer spacing has a direct impact on the fuselage panel weight. It would be also interesting to quantify the effects of frame pitch and fuselage diameter on the design of fuselage panels.

10. Acknowledgement

Authors of this paper would like to acknowledge the financial support of this research by NSERC (Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada), FQRNT (Fonds de recherche du Québec - Nature et technologies), and Bombardier Aerospace. The authors would like to thank all the colleagues of the Advanced Structure group of Bombardier Aerospace for their unwavering unconditional support.

References

[1] A. Jackson, "Advanced composite structural concepts and material technology for primary aircraft structures," *Proceedings of The First NASA Advanced Composites Technology Conference*, Hampton, VA, Part 1, pp 39-69, 1991

[2] D. Paul, L. Kelly, and V. Venkayya, "Evolution of U.S. military aircraft structures technology," *Journal of Aircraft*, Vol. 39, No. 1, pp 18-29, 2002

[3] R. C. Rice, J. L. Jackson, J. Bakuckas, S. Thompson, "Metallic materials properties development and standardization (MMPDS)," U.S. Department of Transportation, Washington, DC, Rep. DOT/FAA/AR-MMPDS-01, January 2003

[4] "MIL-HDBK-17-2F, Composite material handbook, Volume 2. Polymer matrix composites materials properties," pp 63-77, 2002

[5] "HexWeb HRH-10 aramid fibre/phenolic honeycomb product data" [online]. Available: http://www.hexcel.com/Resources/DataSheets/Honeycomb-Data-Sheets/HRH_10_eu.pdf

[6] "SynCore design guide: an aerospace technology guide" [online]. Available: http://www.loctite.co.th/tht/content_data/LT3729_TT_Aerospace_Syncore_Design_Guide.pdf